

Dermatologic conditions as risk factors for cardiovascular disease

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Abstract

Skin diseases (SDs) represent a heterogeneous group of conditions with an overall high prevalence and significant impact on the quality of life of patients. They are also associated with a heavy economic burden for public health systems. Abundant evidence indicates some SDs significantly increase the overall incidence of major cardiovascular events, in particular acute myocardial infarction. This is particularly true for conditions whose pathophysiology features chronic inflammation, like psoriasis, atopic dermatitis, hidradenitis suppurativa and systemic lupus

erythematosus. These SDs may increase cardiovascular risk (CVR) directly by enhancing, precipitating and perpetuating chronic inflammation; and also indirectly, by way of their association with other CVR factors such as obesity, dyslipidemia, hypertension, hyperglycemia, hyperinsulinemia and diabetes. This review aims to analyze the available evidence regarding SDs and their impact on CVR.

Keywords: Dermatologic diseases, cardiovascular risk, cardiovascular disease, chronic inflammation, psoriasis.

Las enfermedades de la piel (ED) representan un grupo heterogéneo de afecciones con una alta prevalencia general y un impacto significativo en la calidad de vida de los pacientes. Además, se asocian a una importante carga económica para los sistemas de salud pública. Existe abundante evidencia que indica que algunas ED aumentan significativamente la incidencia general de eventos cardiovasculares mayores, en particular el infarto agudo de miocardio. Esto es particularmente cierto en afecciones cuya fisiopatología se caracteriza por la inflamación crónica, como la psoriasis, la dermatitis atópica, la hidradenitis supurativa y el lupus eritematoso sistémico. Estas ED pueden aumentar el riesgo cardiovascular (RCV) directamente al potenciar, precipitar y perpetuar la inflamación crónica; y también indirectamente, mediante su asociación con otros factores de RCV como la obesidad, la dislipidemia, la hipertensión, la hiperglucemia, la hiperinsulinemia y la diabetes. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo analizar la evidencia disponible sobre las ED y su impacto en el RCV.

Palabras clave: Enfermedades dermatológicas, riesgo cardiovascular, enfermedad cardiovascular, inflamación crónica, psoriasis.

study does not include several entities under the label of dermatologic conditions. For instance, melanoma and cutaneous manifestations of lupus are included in cancer and musculoskeletal disorders, respectively⁶. Furthermore, some dermatologic conditions are highly stigmatized, thus, leading to underreporting from patients⁷. At any rate, in the United States, the direct and indirect costs of skin disease in 2013 were \$75 billion and \$11 billion, respectively⁸.

SDs generate a significant financial and QoL burden, not to mention their aesthetic implications. Beyond this, recent evidence suggests some SDs, mainly those related to chronic inflammation, increase patients' cardiovascular risk (CVR)⁹. Historically, psoriasis has been the most studied and accepted condition to increase CVR¹⁰. Furthermore, novel studies suggest other more prevalent conditions, like atopic dermatitis, might be associated with increased CVR¹¹. This new insight regarding SDs could further magnify their financial and QoL impact, as this aspect has yet to be considered in epidemiology and burden research. This review aims to analyze the available evidence regarding SDs and their impact on CVR.

PSORIASIS: A CLASSIC INFLAMMATORY DISORDER LINKED TO CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

The association between CVR and dermatologic conditions was first discovered regarding psoriasis. This is a chronic inflammatory condition that primarily compromises the dermatologic system, affecting around 125 million people worldwide¹². The first report of an association between psoriasis and cardiovascular disease (CVD) dates back to 1978 by McDonald et al.¹³, where they compared the clinical records of 323 psoriatic patients and 325 non-psoriatic patients in order to assess the relative risk of cardiovascular conditions like acute myocardial infarction (AMI). The data obtained suggested that occlusive vascular events were significantly greater in psoriatic patients, and this was particularly true for male subjects. Following this report, similar research has been conducted to further explore how psoriasis is linked to cardiometabolic disease¹⁴.

Psoriasis perfectly exemplifies a human model of chronic generalized inflammation, which in this case is most strongly represented in vascular inflammation, in the form of endothelial damage^{15,16}. Similarly, CVD has been conceptualized as an inflammatory condition; and psoriasis confers a higher CVR, especially for AMI¹⁷. More importantly, these differences in risk are more prominent in younger populations with severe forms of psoriasis^{17,18}. Thus, it has been hypothesized that psoriasis not only increases CVR but also accelerates this risk. It is possible to estimate the severity of psoriasis by assessing the total body surface area (TBSA) affected by psoriatic plaques. Furthermore, a psoriasis severity index score (PSIS) and the TBSA have shown a direct correlation with aortic vascular inflammation, which has been as-

Skin diseases (SDs) are highly prevalent among children and adults and account for the fourth leading cause of nonfatal disease burden globally¹. While only a few are lethal, like Stevens-Johnson syndrome and skin cancer, most of them significantly impact patients' quality of life (QoL)². Moreover, SDs represent a tremendous cost for the individuals suffering from it and the healthcare system, making them a significant public health concern³. Although they are generally known to be very frequent, population-based studies describing the epidemiology of these conditions are relatively scarce. Most available data comes from highly selected populations and small sample studies, making prevalence, incidence, and other epidemiological reports somewhat inconsistent⁴.

In 2013, skin conditions corresponded to nearly 2% of the total global burden of disease. Dermatitis alone amounted to 9.3 million disability-adjusted life years, showing the great extent of dermatologic conditions⁵. Some authors suggest these estimations are likely to be underestimated by several factors. Firstly, the classification system for the Global Burden of Disease (GBD)

sociated with high CVR, especially coronary atherosclerosis¹⁹.

Likewise, inflammation plays a vital role, from the pathogenesis to the end-organ damage associated with hypertension²⁰. Psoriasis and hypertension share important inflammatory pathways²¹. Many studies have reported a significantly greater prevalence and risk of hypertension (HT) in patients with psoriasis^{22,23}; and conversely, HT may be a risk factor for psoriasis²⁴. Similarly, chronic inflammation promotes insulin resistance, thus increasing the risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2)²⁵. Several studies have reported that psoriatic patients are more prone to both hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia compared to controls. Moreover, PSIS and TBSA positively correlate with hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels²⁶.

On the other hand, inflammation can also lead to increased production and decreased clearance of triglycerides (TAG), and alterations of the content and function of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C)^{27,28}. Evidence supports that psoriatic patients have higher triglycerides and lower serum HDL-C than the general population²⁹. Furthermore, HDL-C efflux capacity is impaired in psoriasis and negatively correlates with PSIS and TBSA³⁰. Moreover, patients with psoriasis have been reported to have higher measures of total adiposity and increased visceral, hepatic and epicardial adiposity, which is an independent cardiovascular risk factor^{31,32}. However, the directionality of the correlation between psoriasis and obesity is complex, and likely bidirectional³³.

The CVR of psoriatic patients exceeds the general population's risk; firstly because of pathogenic mechanisms inherent to the conditions and, secondly, because of the increased prevalence of comorbidities with cardiovascular repercussions, like DM and HT^{34,35}.

OTHER SKIN CONDITIONS AND CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE: LOOKING BEYOND THE SURFACE

The link between dermatologic conditions and CVR is not limited to psoriasis, since less severe inflammatory dermatologic conditions have also been reported as risk factors for CVD and major cardiovascular events¹¹. Indeed, atopic dermatitis (AD) has also drawn significant attention concerning CVR. AD, also called eczema, is a chronic, pruritic skin condition closely related to asthma and allergic conditions³⁶. While less severe than psoriasis, AD represents a significantly greater burden since it affects 3-20% of the population, depending on the region and age³⁷. Although it is perceived as relatively benign, AD can significantly decrease patients' QoL by impacting their social, academic, and financial well-being³⁸. More importantly, recent evidence suggests patients with AD have increased CVR. However, currently available reports remain conflicting, and no well-documented mechanism has been pinpointed to underlie the link between AD and CVD, beyond the inherent inflammation process of AD and, possibly, its treatment³⁹.

Ascott et al.⁴⁰ conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of population-based studies assessing the relationship between AD and CVR. Although they found no overall association, they suggest the CVR of these patients may increase as the severity of AD augments. Similarly, a cohort study from the United Kingdom concluded that an association existed between AD and CVD. Patients with AD had a significantly greater risk of stroke, unstable angina, AMI, atrial fibrillation, and heart failure. However, it was impossible to determine if these observations were a direct product of AD or the treatment patients received⁴¹. Likewise, Silverberg et al.⁴², using data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) and the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS), found an association between AD and CVD.

Other dermatologic conditions with cardiovascular impact include hidradenitis suppurativa (HS). HS is a chronic suppurative inflammatory condition affecting apocrine glands in intertriginous areas⁴³. Several comorbidities are associated with HS, including obesity, inflammatory bowel disease, and metabolic syndrome. Likewise, recent studies have shown a clear association between HS and individual metabolic markers like insulin resistance and hyperlipidemia, all of which are independent risk factors for CVD⁴⁴. Sabat et al.⁴⁵ found a significant association between HS and metabolic syndrome (Odds Ratio (OR): 4.46), as well as risk factors such as central obesity (OR: 5.88), hypertriglyceridemia (OR: 2.24) and hyperglycemia (OR: 4.09). Other studies have also found OR values ranging from 2 to 6; however, a causal link remains to be identified, and more studies are needed to provide further insight⁴⁶.

Other skin conditions have also been linked to CVR, also heavily featuring inflammation. However, most of these SDs do not have enough evidence to support them as independent risk factors. Rosacea is an excellent example, since it is closely related to proatherogenic vascular changes and inflammatory pathways⁴⁷. Similar theories have been proposed for bullous pemphigoid, acanthosis nigricans, systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), acne and many others^{11,48}. While the assumptions regarding the cardiovascular impact of the aforementioned conditions have solid pathophysiologic pathways, no significant correlation has been consistently reproduced across studies, with the possible exception of SLE^{9,11,49}. More research is needed to provide further recommendations regarding many SDs and their impact on cardiovascular health.

SDs represent a heterogeneous group of conditions with an overall high prevalence and significant impact on the QoL of patients. In addition, abundant evidence indicates some SDs significantly increase the overall incidence of major cardiovascular events. The latter is particularly true for conditions whose pathophysiology features chronic inflammation, like psoriasis, HS, AD, and SLE. While some studies suggest other conditions may increase CVR, they lack statistical significance and power. In light of the relationship between CVR and certain SDs, recommendations to decrease such CVR should be made specifically for these groups of patients. This may provide an invaluable decrease in the incidence of CVD in this group of patients and improve their overall QoL.

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